

SLA SECOND LANGUAGE ACQUISITION MOTIVATIONAL DYNAMICS IN LANGUAGE LEARNING - BOOK REVIEW

Ozlem Yagcioglu¹

Full-time instructor, Dokuz Eylul University,
Modern Languages Department, Izmir, Turkey

In this article, I would like to write the review of the book, entitled **Motivational Dynamics in Language Learning**. It was edited by **Zoltán Dörnyei, Peter D. MacIntyre and Alastair Henry**. The International Standard Book Numbers of this book are as follows: ISBN-13:978-1-78309-256-7 (hbk) and ISBN-13:978-1-78309-255-0 (pbk). This book has 429 pages and two parts. Before the first part of this book, there is a foreword and an introduction part. Before foreword, the names of the contributors of this book and their short biographies are given. Contributors of this book are listed by Dörnyei, MacIntyre and Henry (2015: p.p. ix-x-xi-xii-xiii) as follows:

Ali H. Al-Hoorie is a Lecturer in the English Language Centre, Jubail Industrial College, Saudi Arabia. His interests include learning motivation, learning theories, complexity theory and research methodology. He is currently a PhD student at the University of Nottingham.

Kumiko Arano received her Master's Degree from the Graduate School of Foreign Language Education and Research at Kansai University in March 2013. Her research interests include the role of motivation in EFL and its application to teaching practice. She continues to pursue her interest in English teaching in her current position as an educator at a public high school in Japan.

Kyoko Baba is an Associate Professor at Kinjo Gakuin University in Nagoya, Japan, where she teaches undergraduate and MA courses. She completed her PhD at the Ontario Institute for Studies in Education at the University of Toronto in 2007. Her research interests include the learning of L2 writing skills (with a focus on the

¹ Correspondence: email ozlemygcgl@gmail.com

instructed context), the lexical features of L2 learners' language production and complexity theory.

Letty Chan is a Research Student in applied linguistics at the University of Nottingham. Her current research interests include the L2 Motivational Self System, faith and L2 identity, the use of imagery in the L2 classroom and Dynamic Systems Theory. She has taught academic English at both the University of Hong Kong and Nottingham Trent University. She has published papers on vision and imagery.

Kata Csizér holds a PhD in Language Pedagogy and works as a lecturer in the Department of English and Applied Linguistics at Eötvös University, Budapest, where she teaches various L2 motivation courses. Her main field of research interest focuses on the socio-psychological aspects of L2 learning and teaching, as well as second and foreign language motivation. She has published over 50 academic papers on various aspects of L2 motivation and has co-authored three books, including *Motivational Dynamics, Language Attitudes and Language Globalisation: A Hungarian Perspective* (2006, *Multilingual Matters*, with Zoltán Dörnyei and Nóra Németh).

Kees de Bot is Chair of Applied Linguistics at the University of Groningen in the Netherlands and research fellow at the University of the Free State in South Africa. His current research interests include the application of Dynamic Systems Theory in the study of Second Language Development, language attrition, the effectiveness of bilingual schools in the Netherlands and the history of Applied Linguistics (1980-2010).

Zoltán Dörnyei is Professor of Psycholinguistics at the School of English, University of Nottingham. He has published widely on various aspects of second language acquisition and language learning motivation, and he is the author of several books, including *Research Methods in Applied Linguistics* (2007, Oxford University Press), *The Psychology of Second Language Acquisition* (2009, Oxford University Press), *Teaching and Researching Motivation* (2nd edn, 2011, Longman, with Ema Ushioda), *Motivating Learning* (2013, Longman, with Jill Hadfield) and *Motivating Learners, Motivating Teachers: Building Vision in the Language Classroom* (2014, Cambridge University Press, with Magdalena Kubanyiova).

Tammy Gregerson is a Professor of TESOL at the University of Northern Iowa where she specializes in language teaching methodology. She taught English and trained teachers in Chile for 15 years and has also been involved in teacher education programs and conferences in Spain, Russia, Poland, United Arab Emirates, Italy, Portugal, France, Belgium and Austria. Her research interests include individual differences and nonverbal communication in applied linguistics. She is co-author of *Capitalizing on Language Learners' Individuality: From Premise to Practice* (2014, *Multilingual Matters*, with Peter MacIntyre)

Alastair Henry teaches at University West, Sweden, and has a PhD in Language Education from the University of Gothenburg. His research has focused on motivation in third language learning and gender differences in L2 motivation.

Phil Hiver is a Lecturer in the Department of English Language Teaching at the International Graduate School of English, Seoul, where he teaches courses in language pedagogy and materials development. His research interests include the broad areas of teacher motivation and development, and psychological constructs in instructed second language acquisition using DST and case-based methods.

Zana Ibrahim is a PhD Student Researcher in the School of English Studies, University of Nottingham. He is the recipient of a Fulbright Scholarship and obtained his Master's degree in TESOL from the Indiana University of Pennsylvania. He has worked in the field of foreign language teaching and translation. His research interests include Directed Motivational Currents, Dynamic Systems Theory and ESL syllabus design and materials development.

Kay Irie is a Professor at Gakushuin University, Tokyo where she is developing CLIL-based English program. She also teaches in the Graduate College of Education at Temple University Japan. Her current research interests include learner autonomy and motivation in language education. She is a co-editor of *Realizing Autonomy: Practice and Reflection in Language Education Contexts* (2012, Palgrave Macmillan).

Diana Larsen-Freeman is Professor Emerita at the University of Michigan, Ann Arbor, and a Visiting Senior Fellow at the University of Pennsylvania. She is also a Distinguished Senior Faculty Fellow at the Graduate SIT Institute in Brattleboro, Vermont. Her interests include second language development, English grammar, language teaching and language teacher education.

Peter D. MacIntyre is a Professor of Psychology at Cape Breton University. His research focuses on the dynamic changes in emotion and cognition that take place as part of the psychology of communication. Recently, he co-authored *Capitalizing on Language Learners' Individuality: From Premise to Practice* (2014, Multilingual Matters, with Tammy Gregersen) as a guide to translating theory into classroom action. He teaches a variety of courses, including advanced research methods, human sexuality, personality, advanced social psychology, motivation and emotion, and positive psychology.

Sarah Mercer teaches at the University of Graz, Austria where she has been working since 1998. She has a PhD from the University of Lancaster and her research interests include all aspects of the psychology surrounding the foreign language learning experience, focusing in particular on the self. She is the author of *Towards an Understanding of Language Learner Self-Concept* (2011, Springer) and is co-editor of *Psychology for Language Learning* (2012, Palgrave MacMillan, with Stephen Ryan and

Marion Williams) and *Multiple Perspectives on the Self* (2014, *Multilingual Matters*). She is also an associate editor at the journal *System*.

Christine Muir is a Postgraduate Teaching Fellow at the University of Nottingham and is currently completing her PhD under the supervision of Professor Zoltán Dörnyei. She graduated from the University of Edinburgh with an MSc in Language Teaching, having previously spent time teaching English in Russia, Finland, the Czech Republic and the UK. Her current research interests include Directed Motivational Currents, vision theory, time perspective and Dynamic Systems Theory.

Ryo Nita is an Associate Professor at Nagoya Gakuin University, Japan, where he teaches second language acquisition in the Faculty of Foreign Studies. He received his PhD from the University of Warwick in 2007. His recent research focuses on changes in second language performance (both oral and written) and L2 motivation from a complex dynamic systems perspective.

Katalin Piniel is an Assistant Professor at the Department of English and Applied Linguistics at Eötvös University, Budapest, where she obtained her PhD in Language Pedagogy. She teaches courses in academic writing, research methodology, individual differences in language learning, language anxiety and language testing at both graduate and undergraduate levels. Her research interests include the interrelationship of individual differences in foreign language learning and language anxiety.

Stephen Ryan is a Professor in the School of Economics at Senshu University, Tokyo. His research and publications address a range of issues relating to the psychology of second language learning, with a recent interest in the motivational roles of narrative and the imagination in language learning. He is co-editor (with Sarah Mercer and Marion Williams) of *Psychology for Language Learning: Insights from Theory, Research and Practice* (2012, Palgrave Macmillan).

John H. Schumann is Distinguished Professor (Emeritus) of Applied Linguistics and former chair of the Department of Applied Linguistics and TESL at UCLA. His research includes language acquisition, the neurobiology of language, the neurobiology of learning and language evolution. He is co-author of *The International Instinct: The Evolution and Acquisition of Language* (2009, OUP) and *The Neurobiology of Learning* (2004, Erlbaum). He is co-editor of *Exploring the Interactional Instinct* (2013, OUP). He is also the author of *The Neurobiology of Affect in Language* (1997, Blackwell).

Alicia Serroul is Student Researcher at Cape Breton University. Alicia is completing her honours degree in psychology (BA, 2014) on the topic of human-computer interaction regarding social stances.

Emma Ushioda is an Associate Professor and Director of Graduate Studies at the Centre for Applied Linguistics, University of Warwick, UK. Her research interests are

motivation for language learning and intercultural engagement, learner autonomy, sociocultural theory and teacher development. Recent publications include International Perspectives on Motivation: Language Learning and Professional Challenges (2013, Palgrave Macmillan), Teaching and Researching Motivation (2011, Longman, co-authored with Zoltán Dörnyei) and Motivation, Language Identity and the L2 Self (2009, Multilingual Matters, co-edited with Zoltán Dörnyei).

Marjolijn Verspoor gained her PhD in 1991 from the University of Leiden and is Associate Professor at the University of Groningen, Netherlands, and at the University of the Free State, South Africa. Her research is focused on second language development from a usage-based, dynamic systems perspective and on second language instruction drawing on dynamic usage-based principles.

Frea Waninge is a PhD student at the University of Nottingham, where she researches emotion and motivation and works as a teaching assistant and lab manager at the Centre of Research for Applied Linguistics. Her research interests include the interaction of emotion, motivation and cognition, the L2 learning experience and motivation in young language learners.

Tomoko Yashima is a Professor of Applied Linguistics and Intercultural Communication at Kansai University. Her research interests include L2 learning motivation, affect and language identity. Her studies have been published in journals such as *The Modern Language Journal*, *Language Learning*, *System* and *Psychological Reports*. She is the author of several books published in Japanese including *Motivation and Affect in Foreign Language Communication* (2004, Kansai University Press) and has published a Japanese translation of Zoltán Dörnyei's *Questionnaires in L2 Research*.

Chenjing (Julia) You is a PhD student in the School of English, University of Nottingham, where she also obtained her Master's degree. In China, she has worked as an Associate Professor in the field of foreign language teaching and has also taught English at several high schools for more than 10 years. Her research interests include second language motivation, vision and imagery, and Complex Dynamic Systems Theory.

The foreword part of this book has five pages and it was written by John H. Schumann. As Schumann states (2015: p.xv):

“This book is a milestone in the study of motivation. It brings together several important advances. First, it recognizes dynamic systems theory as the epistemological basis for conceptualizing motivation. It provides an extensive tutorial on dynamic systems. It introduces research methodologies that allow, on several timescales, the study of individual motivational trajectories in second language acquisition (SLA). The book

challenges several assumptions about 'scientific' research in SLA. One is the assumption that truth is found in the study of inter-individual variability among large numbers of subjects. Another is that casual effects are either singular or few in number and that they operate linearly. An additional assumption is that categories and their labels refer to clearly identifiable entities in the world. The adoption of dynamic systems theory (DST) allows, indeed, compels us to eschew notions of single causes, linear casualty, immutable categories and highly specified endpoints."

The first page of the book starts with the introduction part. The title of the introduction part of this book is **Applying Complex Dynamic Systems Principles to Empirical Research on L2 Motivation**. The authors of the introduction part of this book are Zoltán Dörnyei, Peter D. MacIntyre and Alastair Henry. The introduction part of this book has seven pages. In this part, it has been mentioned by Dörnyei, MacIntyre and Henry (2015: p. 1):

" When nonlinear system dynamics was introduced into second language acquisition (SLA) research-under various rubrics such as chaos theory (Larsen-Freeman, 1997), emergentism (Ellis & Larsen-Freeman, 2006), dynamic systems theory (de Bot et al., 2007) and complexity theory (Larsen-Freeman & Cameron, 2008)- the new approach, which may be seen as the 'dynamic turn' in SLA, resonated with many scholars because nonlinear system Dynamics appeared to nicely describe several puzzling language learning phenomena. To offer but one illustration, the so-called' butterfly effect' explained why language teaching input sometimes had considerable impact on the learners' progress, whereas at other times it led only to minimal, if any, uptake. The dynamic principles introduced also made intuitive sense research-wise."

The title of the first part of this book is **Conceptual Summaries**. The first part of this book starts on the 11th page. In this part, Larsen-Freeman (2015: p.11) states that;

"In some ways, the fact that 'theory' is in the name of Complex Dynamic Systems Theory (CDST) is unfortunate. While the use of 'theory' is not incorrect, it tends to underestimate what is on offer. The purpose of this chapter is two-fold: First, to introduce ten lessons from CDST has far-reaching consequences, beyond what one might normally expect with a new theory. The fact is that CDST has fundamentally challenged our goal for research and our way of conducting it. No longer can we be content with Newtonian reductionism, a Laplacian clockwork universe with its deterministic predictability, and the use of statistics to generalize from the behaviour of population samples to individuals."

Given its potential for encouraging entirely new regimes of thought, it has been called a paradigm by some, by others a metatheory, and by still others a theoretical framework. The point is that its influence and its promise extend beyond that of most theories.

This is because CDST is transdisciplinary in two senses of the term. It is transdisciplinary in that it has been used in many different disciplines to investigate issues ranging from the spread of disease, to the contribution of diversity in ecologies, to the formation of ant colonies and to an explanation for the demise of an ancient Pueblo people."

In the same part of this book, in the tenth unit, it has been mentioned by Dörnyei, Ibrahim and Muir (2015: p. 95):

"Most people will, at some point or other, have come across a curious phenomenon whereby somebody suddenly embarks on a project, invests a great deal of time and energy in it for a period of time and, as a result, often achieves something quite remarkable. Take, for example, an overweight university professor (specialised in motivation), who is coming to terms with the fact that all the time spent sitting in front of his computer, as well as attending delicious business lunches and sumptuous conference dinners, has been causing a very noticeable increase in his waistline, until one day something changes: his friends and family are surprised to see that he has enrolled in a gym, his evening pudding has turned into a single yoghurt, and at conference buffet lunches he does not go back for seconds (and even his first plate contains an uncharacteristic amount of vegetables). As a result, he loses over 20 pounds over a period of three months. Alternatively, consider for example a second language (L2)-related situation when someone decides to start learning a foreign language in preparation for an extended foreign trip, and becomes embroiled in the process to such an extent that she spends virtually all her free time studying the language, while also purchasing dictionaries and computer software to direct her learning, as well as voraciously reading guidebooks and surfing L2 websites to familiarize herself with the L2 culture and environment. In an extreme case she might bore family and friends rigid by talking of the trip and the language incessantly, may dream of the journey at night and cannot help but rehearse the language even while lying in bed."

The sub-titles of the first part of this book are as follows: **2-** Ten 'Lessons' from Complex Dynamic Systems Theory: What is on Offer by *Diana Larsen-Freeman* **3-** Attractor States by *Phil Hiver* **4-** Rates of Change: Timescales in Second Language Development by *Kes de Bot* **5-** Initial Conditions by *Marjolijn Verspor* **6-** Context and

Complex Dynamic Systems Theory by *Ema Ushioda* 7- Human Agency: Does the Beach Ball Have Free Will by *Ali H. Al-Hoorie* 8- Social Network Analysis and Complex Dynamic Systems by *Sarah Mercer* 9- The Dynamics of Possible Selves by *Alastair Henry* 10- Directed Motivational Currents: Regulating Complex Dynamic Systems through Motivational Surges by *Zoltán Dörnyei, Zana Ibrahim and Christine Muir*.

The title of the second part of this book is **Empirical Studies**. The second part of this book starts on the 109th page. In the second part of this book, Chan, Dörnyei and Henry (2015: p.p. 243-244-245) denote that;

“At the beginning of the teacher focus group, the first author introduced the aims of the study, its method and the schedule of the session to the teacher participants. In order to facilitate the identification of learner archetypes, a list of adjectives in English (both positive and negative) was presented as a set of illustrative descriptors designed to reflect learners’ emotions, cognition, motivation and behaviour. A specific example of a possible learner archetype was also provided and the participants were encouraged to think of typical student’s representative of this type. After the introduction, the teachers were first asked in pairs, and then in the whole group, to brainstorm and come up with other possible archetypes. The descriptions of the seven learner archetypes generated by the teacher focus group are as follows.

- (1) **A highly competitive and motivated student, with some negative emotions.** According to the teachers’ focus group, students in this archetype are intelligent, motivated individuals with a noticeable competitive edge. They tend to have high expectations of their teachers and expect to be given new and challenging activities and materials in class. They reflect on things to a great degree and tend to be somewhat nervous.
- (2) **An unmotivated student with lower-than-average English proficiency.** This archetype is unique in a way because, although these students are placed in an elite English class, their proficiency in English is not comparable with their peers and they tend to be lower achievers in general. They are described as quiet, sombre and lacking confidence. In comparison to their elite class peers, they are perceived to be ‘lazy’, ‘not hardworking’ and that their schoolwork tends to be rather ‘slapdash’.
- (3) **A happy-go-lucky student with low-English proficiency (usually found in the Year 7 remedial classes).** The teachers’ focus group described this archetype as represented by someone who is highly motivated in general and enjoys going to school, but someone who at the same time struggles with English and keeps having to ask questions in order to understand what is going

on in the class. Although their grades are relatively poor, their emotional stability and happy-go-lucky disposition allow them to move beyond their failures. As a result, setbacks in their schoolwork do not seem to frustrate them.

- (4) **A mediocre student with little L2 motivation.** According to our teacher informants, this is a very common archetype. Despite having the abilities to achieve, students belonging to this category will often only do the minimum required of them owing to a lack of motivation. In English classes, they are receptive, well-behaved and can function well without any problems. They nearly always pass their tests. Nonetheless, they are perceived as not taking their learning particularly seriously and not possessing clear expectations for themselves. They are stable in their emotions, tending to be calm and placid.
- (5) **A motivated yet distressed student with low English proficiency.** This archetype was described as being largely represented by quiet female students who tend to be hardworking, diligent and motivated. Students in this group tend to complete the tasks teachers ask them to do, submit all their homework on time and take comprehensive notes in class. However, they are also slow and rather rigid in their learning. What few learning strategies they have (e.g. their methods of revising for tests) tend to be ineffective. Consequently, these learners are unhappy with their work in that it fails to produce any enduring results. It is not uncommon for students in this archetype to be brought to tears when receiving a test paper and realizing that the considerable effort they have invested in their studies has not borne fruit.
- (6) **A 'perfect' English learner.** Teachers saw this archetype-usually found in the elite classes of the school-as the L2 student who is intelligent, independent and focused. Such learners have a great sense of responsibility and are willing to carry out the tasks assigned to them; they are the type of students who, the teachers say, will readily give them a set of notes when the teacher has misplaced his or hers. They are confident, highly motivated, emotionally stable, have a genuine interest in the subject and engage eagerly in autonomous learning (e.g. they keep a vocabulary log, write grammar notes and keep a journal in English).
- (7) **An unmotivated student with poor English proficiency.** This student type is very similar to the second of the archetypes in several respects, including being reserved, withdrawn, lazy and lacking motivation. Students belonging to this category are also said to be unhappy and lack confidence in their abilities. Teachers see them as difficult and their work as substandard. What makes them

different from the second archetype is that they have lower-than-average language learning abilities even in a regular (i.e. non-elite) class."

The following are the sub-titles of the second part of this book: **11-** Motivation on a Per-Second Timescale: Examining Approach Avoidance Motivation During L2 Task Performance by *Peter D. MacIntyre and Alicia Serroul* **12-** Dynamics of the Self: A Multilevel Nested Systems Approach by *Sarah Mercer* **13-** Changes in Motivation, Anxiety and Self-efficacy During the Course of An Academic Writing Seminar by *Katalin Piniel and Kata Csizér* **14-** Motivation, Emotion and Cognition: Attractor States in the Classroom by *Fea Waninge* **15-** Once Burned, Twice Shy: The Dynamic Development of System Immunity in Teachers by *Phil Hiver* **16-** Learner Archetypes and Signature Dynamics in the Language Classroom: A Retrodictive Qualitative Modelling Approach to Studying L2 Motivation by *Letty Chan, Zoltán Dörnyei and Alastair Henry* **17-** I Can See a Little Bit of You on Myself: A Dynamic Systems Approach to the Inner Dialogue between Teacher and Learner Selves by *Tammy Gregersen and Peter D. MacIntyre* **18-** Understanding EFL Learners' Motivational Dynamics: A Three-Level Model from a Dynamic Systems and Sociocultural Perspective by *Tomoko Yashima and Kumiko Arano* **19-** The Dynamics of L3 Motivation: A Longitudinal Interview/Observation-Based Study by *Alastair Henry* **20-** Study Abroad and the Dynamics of Change in Learner L2 Self-Concept by *Kay Irie and Stephen Ryan* **21-** Self-Regulation in the Evolution of the Ideal L2 Self: A Complex Dynamic Systems Approach to the L2 Motivational Self System by *Ryo Nitta and Kyoko Baba* **22-** The Dynamics of L2 Imagery in Future Motivational Self-Guides *Chenjing (Julia) You and Letty Chan* **23-** Conclusion: Hot Enough to be Cool: The Promise of Dynamic Systems Research by *Peter D. MacIntyre, Zoltán Dörnyei and Alastair Henry*.

This book presents different views on motivational dynamics in language learning. Apart from learning a second language, it also gives ideas and views on learning the third language. A dynamic approach to motivation is handled and explained in terms of different aspects of the classroom teachers have in their classes. Motivational factors are explained and sample interviews are shared. How anxiety and self-efficacy change motivation during the courses are also explained. This book can be read by all of the foreign language teachers, language teacher-trainers, professors or researchers to develop their views on motivation and motivational factors. The data-based studies help us to learn useful research models on applied linguistics and second language acquisition.

In conclusion, it can be said that this book offers empirical research studies which investigate the dynamics of language learning motivation and it shows the world

how and why motivation is a crucial factor in learning a foreign language effectively. Depicting my teaching areas and experience, I can say that this book is very useful for anyone who is involved in learning a foreign language or teaching a foreign language. I hope it will be used and read by the educators who teach foreign languages in different countries of the world.

References

1. Chan, L. Dörnyei, Z. and Henry, A. (2015). Results. Phrase one: Identifying Learner Archetypes. *Learner Archetypes and Signature Dynamics in the Language Classroom: A Retrodictive Qualitative Modelling Approach to Studying L2 Motivation*. In Dörnyei, Z., MacIntyre, P. D., and Henry, A. (Edt.). (2015). *SLA Second Language Acquisition. Motivational Dynamics in Language Learning*. p.p. 243-244-245.
2. Dörnyei, Z., MacIntyre, P. D., and Henry, A. (2015). Contributors. *SLA Second Language Acquisition. Motivational Dynamics in Language Learning*. p.p. ix-x-xi-xii-xiii. Multilingual Matters Publications. Bristol: UK, New York: USA, Ontario, Canada.
3. Dörnyei, Z., MacIntyre, P. D., and Henry, A. (2015). Introduction: Applying Complex Dynamic Systems Principles to Empirical Research on L2 Motivation. *SLA Second Language Acquisition. Motivational Dynamics in Language Learning*. p. 1. Multilingual Matters Publications. Bristol: UK, New York: USA, Ontario, Canada.
4. Dörnyei, Z., Ibrahim, Z., and Muir, C. (2015). Directed Motivational Currents: Regulating Complex Dynamic Systems through Motivational Surges. In Dörnyei, Z., MacIntyre, P. D., and Henry, A. (Edt.). (2015). *SLA Second Language Acquisition. Motivational Dynamics in Language Learning*. p.95. Multilingual Matters Publications. Bristol: UK, New York: USA, Ontario, Canada.
5. Larsen-Freeman, D. (2015). Ten 'Lessons' from Complex Dynamic Systems Theory: What is on Offer. In Dörnyei, Z., MacIntyre, P. D., and Henry, A. (Edt.). (2015). *SLA Second Language Acquisition. Motivational Dynamics in Language Learning*. p.11. Multilingual Matters Publications. Bristol: UK, New York: USA, Ontario, Canada.
6. Schumann, J.H. (2015). Foreword. In Dörnyei, Z., MacIntyre, P. D., and Henry, A. (Edt.). (2015). *SLA Second Language Acquisition. Motivational Dynamics in Language*

Learning. p.xv. Multilingual Matters Publications. Bristol: UK, New York: USA,
Ontario, Canada.

Creative Commons licensing terms

Author(s) will retain the copyright of their published articles agreeing that a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (CC BY 4.0) terms will be applied to their work. Under the terms of this license, no permission is required from the author(s) or publisher for members of the community to copy, distribute, transmit or adapt the article content, providing a proper, prominent and unambiguous attribution to the authors in a manner that makes clear that the materials are being reused under permission of a Creative Commons License. Views, opinions and conclusions expressed in this research article are views, opinions and conclusions of the author(s). Open Access Publishing Group and European Journal of Education Studies shall not be responsible or answerable for any loss, damage or liability caused in relation to/arising out of conflicts of interest, copyright violations and inappropriate or inaccurate use of any kind content related or integrated into the research work. All the published works are meeting the Open Access Publishing requirements and can be freely accessed, shared, modified, distributed and used in educational, commercial and non-commercial purposes under a [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License \(CC BY 4.0\)](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/).